

METHODOLOGY OF REMOTE ORGANIZATION OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE AGRICULTURAL SPECIALISTS

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Abstract. *The article describes the educational system organized on the basis of the conditions of distance education and its structural purpose, content, methods, tools and organizational forms of the distance education system.*

Keywords: *qualified personnel, competence, education, distance education, technology, pedagogical technologies, principle and integrated education.*

In the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, important tasks such as "Increasing the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions based on the introduction of international standards for assessing the quality of education and teaching" were defined.

In the coordination and improvement of educational processes with modern developments, the professional training of future agricultural specialists, that is, their professionalism and competence, is specially recognized. Because the modern requirements for ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of training qualified personnel also include the effective organization of innovative and integrated educational processes that serve to form and develop the professional competence of future specialists, including the distance education methodology.

In distance education, the learner and the teacher are in constant communication with the help of specially created educational courses, control forms, electronic communication and other technologies of the Internet, while being spatially separated from each other. Distance education based on the use of Internet technology provides access to the world information and education network.

Distance learning provides an opportunity for all those who want to learn to continuously improve their skills. In the course of such training, the learner learns independent teaching and methodical materials in an interactive mode, passes control, performs control work under the direct guidance of the teacher, and communicates with other learners of the "vertical learning group" in the group.

Various information and communication technologies are used in distance education. For example, if traditional print-based teaching tools (study guide, textbooks) are based on introducing students to new material, interactive audio and video conferences are designed to communicate over a certain period of time, to establish direct and reverse e-mail communication, that is, to send and receive messages. Pre-recorded video lectures allow learners to listen and watch lectures, while fax communication, instant exchange of messages, assignments over the network allows learners to learn through mutual feedback.

The organization of video communications through telecommunications and computer networks, their formation as a means of distance education is a new methodical and technical

training system is creating an opportunity to implement its provision. High-quality video communication is one of the most reliable means of organizing video seminars and video conferences using a computer. Such tools are of great importance in distance training of pedagogues-teachers, in particular, in solving problems related to educational issues with a group of several dozen people, as they provide individual training, methodical support, and effective implementation of innovative technologies. In addition to the listeners' communication through voice and video images, there are opportunities to manage the images on the computer monitor in cooperation with the listener and the pedagogue.

In distance education, this principle is interpreted as the principle of creative description of the listener's cognitive activity. Creative information technology has an interactive nature and requires the listener to apply the description of the received general information to specific situations. The implementation of the scientific principle of teaching in the process of distance education assumes that students will master scientific evidence, concepts and laws, and theories on the content of a certain subject. The scientific principle requires students to develop the skills of scientific research. For this, it is necessary to widely use problem-based educational methods in laboratory and practical training of agricultural sciences. The successful implementation of this principle in distance education serves to ensure the fundamentality of acquired knowledge.

In distance education, the principle of matching the content and complexity of educational materials to the student's level serves to ensure that the students acquire the planned knowledge, skills and competences without mental and physical overload. The principle of taking into account the individual characteristics of the listeners is of great importance in the organization of distance education, and ensures that the structure of the module of distance courses takes into account the psychophysiological, psychological, psychosociological individual characteristics of the listener. The principle of demonstrability means increasing the effectiveness of education by affecting all the senses of a person in education. In distance education, this principle is mainly provided by means of virtualization technology. In particular, it envisages wide use of video films, educational computer programs, and interactive technologies. Demonstration materials and the method of using multimedia tests are widely used and important tools of the principle of demonstration in distance education.

The following are recommended as effective forms of teaching in distance education:

- Online problem lecture;
- video lectures, webinars;
- Online and Offline binary lecture;
- Online and Offline intensive-interactive seminar;
- Remote video training;
- Online interactive tour; seminars; presentation, work in small groups, etc.

It is recommended to use technical tools, express questions, test questions, brainstorming, group thinking, working with small groups, “Insert”, “FSMU”, “Case”, “SWOT-analysis” technology and other interactive educational methods.

In distance education, the necessary tools for theoretical and practical training may consist of the following;

- Blackboard.
- Flipchart.
- Presentation slides.

- Handouts.
- Multimedia set (netbook, TV).
- “Case bank”.
- Textbooks (traditional textbooks, electronic textbooks, manuals, reference books, etc.).
- Educational and methodological manuals in the (computer) network;
- Computer training systems in conventional and multimedia versions;
- Audio and educational information materials;
- Video educational materials;
- Remote laboratory practicums;
- Remote trainers;
- Remote information and knowledge base;
- Remote electronic libraries;
- Teaching tools based on teaching expert systems;
- Educational tools based on geoinformation systems;
- Teaching tools based on virtual reality.

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